

New Aspects of Nitrogen Fixation and Conservation in Soil. Part I.

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In publications from this laboratory, it has been emphasised that light plays an important rôle in many oxidation processes taking place in the soil and that chemical and not microöbial agencies may be active in these reactions (*cf.* Dhar, "Influence of Light on some Biochemical Processes" 1935).

We are carrying on a systematic investigation on different types of nitrogen fixation and in this communication some of our results are recorded. Experiments showing that carbohydrates can conserve soil nitrogen are also recorded in this paper.

Nitrogen Fixation in the Photo-oxidation of Cane sugar mixed with Sterilised Soil in Quartz Vessels.

The cane sugar, the soil and the quartz vessels were sterilised in an autoclave for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours at 20 lb. pressure. In each experiment 25 c. c. of sterile distilled water were added and the quartz vessels were exposed to sunlight. The mouths of the vessels were covered with plugs of sterile cotton wool.

Method of Analysis.—For estimating the ammoniacal nitrogen present in the soil, 50 g. of the soil which was dried in a steam oven was treated with 5 g. of pure potassium chloride and 5 g. of pure magnesium oxide and 50 c. c. of water and distilled for 6 hours on a water-bath and at the same time a rapid current of air, purified by passing through a solution of ferrous sulphate and sulphuric acid, was aspirated. The ammonia was absorbed in two flasks containing standard solutions of sulphuric acid.

For the estimation of nitric nitrogen, the soil from which ammonia was removed by the previous procedure, was treated with one gram of

Devarda's alloy free from ammonia and nitrate and 25 c. c. of 1% sodium hydroxide solution and left overnight for the reduction of nitrite and nitrate to ammonia. When the reduction was complete, the ammonia set free was determined as in the first stage colorimetrically by Nessler's reagent.

The total nitrogen was estimated according to the method of Robinson, McLean and Williams (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1929, 19, 315) by heating 5 g. of well dried and powdered soil with 20 c. c. conc. sulphuric acid, 5 g. fused potassium sulphate and a few crystals of copper sulphate for 4 hours. The ammonium sulphate thus formed was estimated as before. In this method the total carbon is also determined simultaneously by absorbing the sulphur dioxide produced in a standard iodine solution, the excess of which is titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution. The sum of the ammoniacal and nitric nitrogen is known as available nitrogen and the nitrogen obtained according to the modified Kjeldahl's method is the total combined nitrogen. The following results have been obtained.

TABLE I.

Exposed to sunlight in February and March, 1935.

	NH ₃ -N.	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil	0.000734%	0.0035%	0.004234%	0.0458%	0.5055%
100 G. soil + 1 g. cane sugar + 50 c. c. water exposed for 145 hours in 250 c. c. quartz flask.	0.00116	0.00402	0.00518	0.0466	0.7215
100 G. soil + 2 g. cane sugar + 50 c. c. water exposed for 284 hours in 250 c. c. quartz flask.	0.00155	0.00386	0.00541	0.0486	1.2245
100 G. soil + 4 g. cane sugar + 50 c. c. water exposed for 284 hours in 250 c. c. quartz flask.	0.00175	0.00386	0.00561	0.0486	1.7010

TABLE II.

Exposed to sunlight from 30th April to 15th July 1935.
Total exposure for 480 hours.

	NH ₃ -N.	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil	0.000902%	0.00368%	0.00458%	0.0474%	0.5349%
50 G. soil + 2 g. cane sugar + 25 c. c. water in 250 c. c. quartz flask.	0.001646	0.00396	0.005606	0.04921	1.686
50 G. soil + 4 g. cane sugar + 25 c. c. water in 250 c. c. quartz flask.	0.00143	0.0035	0.00493	0.0519	3.012
50 G. soil + 1 g. cane sugar + 25 c. c. water in a quartz boiling tube.	0.001422	0.0035	0.004922	0.0509	0.871
50 G. soil + 4 g. cane sugar + 25 c. c. water in a quartz boiling tube.	0.001454	0.00364	0.005094	0.054	2.998

The foregoing results show that in all cases when cane sugar and sterile soil are exposed to light in quartz vessels, there is an appreciable increase in the total nitrogen and ammonia contents. It appears, therefore, that the energy set free in the photo-oxidation of sugars can fix atmospheric nitrogen in the soil. The researches of Palit and Dhar (*cf.* Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry") show that sugars are oxidised by air when exposed to sunlight. Recently Ghosh and Rakshit (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 357) have obtained similar results.

*Nitrogen Fixation in the Induced and Catalytic Oxidation
of Glucose or Cane Sugar.*

Air aspirated through two Woulf's bottles, one containing a solution of ferrous sulphate in sulphuric acid and the other concentrated sulphuric acid in order to remove the oxides of nitrogen and ammonia and to kill the bacteria, was passed through an Erlenmeyer flask containing a weighed amount of glucose or cane sugar and ferrous hydroxide obtained from 1 g. of ferrous sulphate and an

equivalent amount of caustic potash. After passing air, the amount of ammonia formed was distilled off by adding alkali and heating. The distillate was absorbed in dilute sulphuric acid and the ammonium sulphate estimated colorimetrically by Nessler's reagent. Two Erlenmeyer flasks containing dilute solutions of sulphuric acid were placed next to the flask containing the inductor, the last one for the absorption of ammonia from the atmosphere of the laboratory. The following experimental results have been obtained.

TABLE III.

	Glucose taken.	Glucose oxidised.	Energy set free.	NH ₃ -N obtained.	Energy utilised.	Efficiency.
(a)	1 G.	0.08 g.	300 Cal.	0.000332 g.	0.512 Cal.	1:586
(b)	0.5	0.064	240	0.000270	0.417	1:575
* (c)	0.5	0.079	296	0.000334	0.515	1:574
	Cane sugar taken.	Cane sugar oxidised.				
(a)	1	0.04	158	0.000245	0.378	1:418
(b)	0.5	0.0347	148	0.000241	0.372	1:398
* (c)	0.5	0.0716	283	0.000462	0.713	1:396

* (with one gram sodium hydrogen phosphate).

The results recorded in the foregoing table show that the induced oxidation of glucose or cane sugar by passing air in the absence of bacteria leads to the formation of ammonia using an 1% solution of glucose, 4 mg. of nitrogen are fixed per gram of glucose oxidised by induction, whilst 4.68 mg. of nitrogen are fixed per gram of mannite in its bacterial oxidation (*cf.* Waksman "Soil microbiology" 1927, p. 569). Similar results in 4 mg. of nitrogen fixation have been observed in the induced oxidation of one gram of cane sugar as against 5.9 milligrams in the bacterial fixation (Compare, Lohnis and Pillai. *Centrbl. Bakt.*, 1908 II, 20, 781). It appears, therefore, that the order of the nitrogen fixation caused by the induced oxidation of glucose or cane sugar is practically the same as in the bacterial fixation.

Nitrogen Fixation in the Oxidation of Cane sugar mixed with Soil and Exposed to Sunlight in Dishes.

In these experiments the garden soil was mixed with pure cane sugar and exposed to sunlight in enamelled dishes covered with ordinary glass plates. For the experiments in the dark, the outer surface of the glass plates was covered with a thick coating of Japan black enamel. The following results were obtained.

TABLE IV.

	NH ₃ -N.	Nitric-N.	Total available N.	Total N.	Total C.	
Exposure for 16 hours spread out from 28th August to 7th September 1935.	250 g. soil alone	0.00356%	0.0021%	0.00566%	0.0466%	0.5134%
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar	0.00396	0.0021	0.00606	0.0466	4.932
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 10 g. Na ₃ PO ₄	0.00436	0.0021	0.00644	0.0466	5.202
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.04516	0.00318	0.04834	0.1289	5.721
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 10 g. Na ₃ PO ₄	0.04668	0.00318	0.04986	0.1272	5.610
	250 g. soil + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.03500	0.0070	0.0420	0.1166	0.5133
Exposure for 74 hours from 28th August to 26th September 1935.	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar	0.00520	0.00208	0.00728	0.0482	4.831
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 10 g. Na ₃ PO ₄	0.00538	0.00208	0.00746	0.0482	5.111
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.0450	0.0032	0.0482	0.1198	5.627
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 10 g. Na ₃ PO ₄	0.040	0.0032	0.0432	0.1152	5.610
	250 g. soil + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.010	0.029	0.039	0.070	0.513

TABLE IV (continued).

	NH ₃ -N.	Nitric-N.	Total available N.	Total N.	Total C.	
Exposure for 100 hours from 28th August to 18th November, 1935.	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar.	0.0070	0.00334	0.01034	0.0537	1.532
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 10 g. Na ₃ PO ₄	0.0075	0.00350	0.0110	0.0560	1.411
	250 g. soil + 20 g. canesugar + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.0468	0.0050	0.00518	0.1010	1.872
	250 g. soil + 20 g. cane sugar + 0.5 g. N as (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ + 10 g. Na ₃ PO ₄	0.0483	0.00524	0.05354	0.1152	1.789
	250 g. soil + 0.5 g. N as ammonium sulphate	0.010	0.00280	0.038	0.066	0.513

The above results show that when soil is mixed with cane sugar in presence or absence of sodium phosphate and exposed to sunlight, the ammoniacal, nitric and total nitrogen increase due to the fixation of the atmospheric nitrogen.

In presence of 0.5 g. of ammoniacal nitrogen added as ammonium sulphate to 250 g. soil and 20 g. cane sugar, there is no evidence of nitrogen fixation as the total nitrogen content is 0.101%, whilst the amount actually present should have been 0.1466% (0.1% added as ammonium sulphate and 0.0466% originally present in the soil). It is quite possible that the fixation if any, may have been compensated by the denitrification, which is known to take place under aerobic conditions. Moreover, these experiments show that ammonium sulphate readily undergoes nitrification when mixed with soil and exposed to sunlight in dishes and cane sugar markedly retards this nitrification and also the nitrogen loss observed by exposing ammonium salts to light and air.

Our results recorded in previous papers (*Proc. Acad. Sci. U.P.*, 1934, **4**, 175; 1935, **4**, 330; 1935, **5**, 61) show that the ammoniacal nitrogen goes on increasing up to a limiting value with the time of exposure to sunlight when the exposure is continued. After this period, further exposure to light leads to a decrease of the ammoniacal nitrogen and an increase of nitric nitrogen. But the sum of the nitric and ammoniacal nitrogen is less than that obtained before. This behaviour is due to the loss of nitrogen in the gaseous state caused by the photochemical, catalytic and thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite formed on the soil surface. This type of denitrification is an important soil process taking place when nitrogenous compounds are present in the soil,

which is exposed to light and air. A very important conclusion can be drawn from the experiments published in the foregoing papers, that the amount of ammoniacal nitrogen is always greater in the soil mixed with the energy-rich compounds and receiving sunlight than in those kept in the dark (that is, in blackened vessels).

Fixation of Nitrogen in the Oxidation of Molasses mixed with Soil.

Experiments carried on in dishes.—As molasses contain 30-40% cane sugar and 30% invert sugars, it was felt that the oxidation of this substance in the soil would be an excellent source for obtaining the energy required in nitrogen fixation.

Mixtures of molasses and unsterilised soil and small amount of water were exposed to sunlight during the months of March, to November, 1935, and the carbon, total nitrogen, ammoniacal nitrogen and nitric nitrogen were estimated from time to time. In the following tables corrections were applied for the amount of ammonia introduced with molasses, which contained 0.001% ammoniacal nitrogen but no nitric nitrogen. The following results were obtained.

TABLE V.

Molasses added per kg. of soil.		NH ₃ -N.	Nitric N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.
Exposed for 161 hours.	0 (original soil)	0.000734%	0.0035%	0.004234%	0.0362%	0.4025%
	5 g.	0.000944	0.0040	0.004944	0.0360	0.4521
	10	0.00096	0.0038	0.00476	0.0360	0.5732
	20	0.00106	0.0038	0.00486	0.0360	0.8212
	40	0.00113	0.0038	0.00493	0.0360	1.0640
	75	0.00220	0.0038	0.00600	0.0380	1.5220
	100	0.00222	0.0038	0.00602	0.0460	2.0810
	150	0.00216	0.0038	0.00596	0.0490	3.8840
	190	0.00210	0.0038	0.00590	0.0520	4.4290
	Corresponding dark.	10	0.00111	0.00338	0.00448	0.0362
20		0.00097	0.00376	0.00475	0.0362	0.9287
40		0.00043	0.00376	0.00410	0.0362	1.2310
Exposed for 279 hours.	5 g.	0.00136	0.00412	0.00548	0.0360	0.459
	10	0.00148	0.00412	0.00560	0.0360	0.576
	20	0.00159	0.00412	0.00571	0.0360	0.823
	40	0.00184	0.00412	0.00597	0.0362	1.065
	75	0.00220	0.00400	0.00620	0.0382	1.329
	100	0.00200	0.00324	0.00524	0.0460	1.986
	150	0.00104	0.00284	0.00388	0.0492	3.424
	190	0.00037	0.00224	0.00261	0.0521	4.021

TABLE V (continued).

Corresponding dark.	10 g.	0.00074%	0.00324%	0.00398%	0.0361%	0.552%
	20	0.00051	0.00310	0.00361	0.0361	0.902
	40	0.00041	0.00282	0.00323	0.0361	1.102
Exposed for 850 hours.	5	0.00092	0.00456	0.00548	0.0381	0.412
	10	0.00096	0.00462	0.00558	0.0381	0.542
	20	0.00116	0.00462	0.00578	0.0382	0.671
	40	0.00310	0.00420	0.00720	0.0389	0.912
	75	0.00175	0.00380	0.00555	0.0391	1.213
	100	0.00146	0.00362	0.00508	0.0472	1.321
	150	0.00133	0.00304	0.00437	0.0468	2.321
	190	0.00120	0.00280	0.00400	0.0480	3.280
Corresponding dark.	10	0.00084	0.00320	0.00404	0.0372	0.513
	20	0.00089	0.00316	0.00405	0.0372	0.882
	40	0.00094	0.00316	0.00409	0.0380	1.087
Exposed for 1450 hours.	5	0.00092	0.00452	0.00544	0.0410	0.4125
	10	0.00098	0.00464	0.00562	0.0418	0.4424
	20	0.00118	0.00504	0.00622	0.0433	0.5516
	40	0.00155	0.00490	0.00645	0.0498	0.5827
	75	0.00185	0.00464	0.00649	0.0510	0.6619
	100	0.00162	0.00422	0.00584	0.0525	0.8629
	150	0.00144	0.00396	0.00540	0.0544	1.252
	190	0.00138	0.00324	0.00462	0.0544	2.441
Corresponding dark.	10	0.00084	0.00344	0.00428	0.0380	0.500
	20	0.00090	0.00336	0.00426	0.0380	0.815
	40	0.00096	0.00344	0.00440	0.0380	0.981

The results recorded in the foregoing table show that in all cases when molasses is added to the soil, which is properly aerated, there is an appreciable increase in its ammonia and total nitrogen contents. In these cases also, like those with cane sugar, there is greater increase of ammonia in the vessels exposed to sunlight than in those kept in the dark. The amount of ammonia formed goes on increasing up to a limiting value with increase of exposure. In all these experiments the total carbon goes on decreasing with time.

Field experiments on the application of molasses to soil.—In these experiments, known weights of molasses were added to a definite area of the soil in the field. In some experiments, the

soils were dug once a week, whilst in others the soil was kept unstirred in order to investigate the influence of aeration. The following results were obtained.

TABLE VI.

3600 Kg. of molasses added per acre of land on 30-7-35.

	NH ₃ -N.	Nitric N.	Available N.	Total. N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Original soil.	0.00374%	0.00334%	0.00708%	0.0466%	0.542%	30- 7-35
	0.00618	0.00320	0.00938	0.0467	0.673	24- 8-35
	0.00670	0.00350	0.01020	0.0467	0.651	3- 9-35
	0.00554	0.00445	0.00999	0.0467	0.653	21- 9-35
	0.00590	0.00500	0.01090	0.0485	0.543	14-10-35
	0.00468	0.00608	0.01076	0.0482	0.543	6-11-35
	0.00464	0.00608	0.01072	0.0488	0.544	17-12-35
	0.00480	0.00598	0.01078	0.0482	0.548	15- 1-36

7200 Kg. of molasses per acre added on 30-7-35.

Original soil.	0.00350	0.00280	0.00630	0.0462	0.515	30- 7-35
	0.00508	0.00262	0.00770	0.0467	0.720	24- 8-35
	0.00724	0.00282	0.00906	0.0467	0.714	3- 9-35
	0.00768	0.00382	0.01150	0.0467	0.711	21- 9-35
	0.00734	0.00400	0.01134	0.0492	0.543	14-10-35
	0.00500	0.00668	0.01168	0.0518	0.543	6-11-35
	0.00488	0.00700	0.01188	0.0520	0.544	17-12-35
	0.00480	0.00782	0.01262	0.0522	0.548	15- 1-36

10800 Kg. of molasses per acre added on 5-8-35.

Original soil	0.00560%	0.00372%	0.00932	0.0522%	0.581	5- 8-35
	0.00612	0.00344	0.00956	0.0579	1.366	24- 8-35
	0.00776	0.00370	0.01146	0.0582	1.238	3- 9-35
	0.01094	0.00358	0.01452	0.0583	1.131	21- 9-35
	0.01028	0.00362	0.01390	0.0588	1.086	14-10-35
	0.00822	0.00576	0.01398	0.0611	0.985	6-11-35
	0.0070	0.0124	0.0194	0.0622	0.821	17-12-35
	0.0056	0.0132	0.0188	0.0624	0.812	15- 1-36

In these field experiments, there is also definite evidence of nitrogen fixation in the soil on the addition of molasses, as there is increase in the available and total nitrogen.

Molasses added to soil in heaps-composts with molasses.—A heap of soil weighing 167 kg. was mixed with 12 kg. of molasses (A) and another heap weighing 174 kg. was treated with 6 kg. of molasses (B) and exposed to air and light. For better aeration, the heaps were stirred frequently after addition of water. The molasses was added on 18th February, 1935 and exposed to sun till the end of June and then removed to a verandah of the laboratory before the rains set in. The following results were obtained.

TABLE VII.

	NH ₃ -N.	Nitric-N.	Total avail- able N.	Total N.	Total C.
Original soil	0.00865%	0.00582%	0.01447%	0.0458	0.5055
Heap (A) analysed 18.3.35	0.01646	0.00594	0.0224	0.0538	1.9922
Heap (B) " " "	0.00934	0.00594	0.01528	0.0504	1.2380
Heap (A) analysed on 18.4.35	0.0140	0.0058	0.0198	0.0540	—
Heap (B) " " "	0.0116	0.0058	0.0174	0.0512	—
Heap (A) analysed on 20.9.35	0.0175	0.00822	0.02572	0.09005	1.0514
Heap (B) " " "	0.0140	0.00736	0.02136	0.09	1.035

The above results show that when molasses is added to soil in heaps and exposed to air and light, the available and the total nitrogen are considerably increased. The total nitrogen is double that of the original amount present in the soil before the addition of molasses. Hence considerable fixation of nitrogen takes place and excellent composts are prepared with molassed soils, of which the carbon-nitrogen ratio becomes normal and attains the value 11.5.

Residual Effect of Molasses added to Fields.

The following results show that molasses when added to the soil in fields produces residual effects.

TABLE VIII.

Plot A		Plot B	Plot C
1800 G. of molasses per acre added on 25-9-34 and then wheat grown. Molassed again at the rate of 3600 g. per acre on 30-4-35 and analysed on 6-5-35.		Original unmolassed but wheat grown. Molassed at the rate of 3600 kg. per acre on 30-4-35 and analysed on 6-5-35.	Control unmolassed, wheat grown, analysed on 6-5-35.
NH ₃ N	0.006%	0.0058%	0.0051%
Nitric N	0.0037%	0.0032	0.0029
Total N	0.0321%	0.0272	0.0224
Total C	0.5428%	0.5121	0.2621

The foregoing results show that Plot A, which has been molassed twice, contains more available and total nitrogen than Plot B, which has been molassed once and Plot C, which has not been molassed at all.

The foregoing results obtained with molasses, when mixed with soil, show that there is an appreciable increase in the total nitrogen and ammonia contents; the amount of ammonia goes on increasing up to a limiting value, when it decreases. But at this stage the nitrate content increases appreciably due to the oxidation of the ammonium salts formed by nitrogen fixation. When the amounts of molasses added to the soil are not large, the maximum amount of ammonia to be formed due to nitrogen fixation in the soil is reached within two months. After this stage the nitrate increases due to oxidation of the ammonium salts produced from the nitrogen fixation in the soil and there is loss of the total available nitrogen and the carbon-nitrogen ratio approaches the 11 : 1 value. Hence, it is concluded that at the stage when the nitrate content of the soil begins to increase appreciably, the soil is most suitable for the sowing of crops. When larger quantities of molasses are added to the soil in the fields, more time is required to attain the stage of nitrate increase. For example, from the results recorded in Table VI, it will be seen that in the plot in which 270 maunds of molasses per acre were added, the largest amount of ammonia was fixed but the time required in reaching the maximum was about 3 months. Similarly in the experiments with molasses and soil kept in dishes, the maximum increase of ammonia is attained after a longer exposure to sunlight in those dishes containing larger amounts of molasses than those with smaller amounts. Thus with 10 grams of molasses when added to a kilogram of soil the maximum amount of ammonia formation is reached after 279 hours of exposure to sun light spread over 75 days, whilst with 40 grams, the maximum is reached after 850 hours of exposure spread over 4 months. It is clear, therefore, that if the cultivator can afford to wait and can use large amounts of molasses better results are expected than with smaller amounts. Using 270 maunds of molasses per acre of land and if digging or turning over of the soil is continued for about 3 months, once in 10 days, excellent results are expected. With smaller amounts varying from 90 to 180 maunds of molasses per acre, an interval of 8 to 12 weeks with occasional digging ought to be sufficient, because the maximum ammonia formation in these cases is within the above interval. It is well

known that the amount of nitrogen fixation in a bacterial culture of *Azotobacter* is quantitatively measured by the ammonia formed. Hence, the evidence of nitrogen fixation in our experiments when molasses of cane sugar is added to the soil is quite definite, because there is not only considerable increase of ammoniacal nitrogen but simultaneously the total nitrogen is also increased. Moreover, in a recent communication, we have shown that in soils, the available nitrogen increases with the increase in total nitrogen.

Our experimental results show that when the soil is not properly aerated after the addition of molasses, the acidity increases and the nitrogen fixation is less.

Many people have tried to use molasses in increasing soil fertility but uniformly good results could not be obtained as will be evident from the following lines:—

“Increased yields of sugarcane have followed the application of molasses to soils at the Station Agronomique and on Mr. Ebbels' estate in Mauritius, where the residual effect is well shown, and also in Antigua. Peck in Hawaii, on the other hand, observed marked losses of nitrate, as also did Harrison in British Guiana.”

“Laboratory investigations in humid climates suffer from the difficulty that the soils already contain so much nitrogen that small changes are difficult to measure accurately, and there are losses of nitrogen which counterbalance any fixation. Investigation would be easier in some of the soils very poor in nitrogen found in hot, arid conditions. Rigid incontestable proof could be furnished only by a demonstrated gain in nitrogen effected by *Azotobacter*, all other possibilities being ruled out. This proof has not yet been forthcoming” (Russell “Soil Conditions and Plant Growth,” 1932 pp. 342-44).

“In view of the fact that the energy added to the soil is not directly available to the nitrogen-fixing bacteria and that small amounts of available nitrogen are always present in the soil, and the error in the laboratory determination of total nitrogen by the Kjeldahl method is greater than the possible amount of nitrogen fixed by non-symbiotic bacteria, we are still unable to decide the question definitely.” (Waksman, “Soil Microbiology” 1927, p. 587).

“Wide use is being made in systems of agriculture of the bacteria, which work with legumes, but the nitrogen fixing power of those which work outside the plant is as yet not utilised extensively by man, since the methods of controlling them are not well understood”

(Miller:, " The Soil and its Management " 1924, p. 203). A. Koch, J. Litzendorff, F. Krull, and A. Alves (*J. Landw.*, 1907, 88, 355) have reported nitrogen fixation in plates and pots with dextrose but Pfeiffer and Blanck (*Landw. Versuchs—Stat.*, 1912, 78, 375) could not obtain any nitrogen fixation with sugar. According to Hutchinson (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1918, 9, 92) sugars show beneficial results in autumn but not in spring.

Dr. H. W. Kerr has reported the following yield of sugarcane on applying 10 tons of molasses per acre in the Bundaberg farm in Queensland.

Without molasses	...	...	22.7 tons per acre.
10 tons molasses	...	...	37.1 tons per acre.

On the other hand, Crabtree working in the Fairy Mead farm in Queensland did not find any beneficial effect with molasses (Proc. Second Annual Conference of Queensland Society of Sugar-cane Technologists, 1932). On applying molasses to the growing crop, no beneficial effect was obtained at Pusa. Recently, an increase of yield to the extent of 36% has been reported at the Shahjahanpur Government Farm on applying 270 maunds of molasses per acre in the cultivation of sugarcane, before planting. Messrs Parry & Co. Ltd., of Madras has also obtained an increase of 40% in the yield of sugarcane. But when molasses was added to the growing crop, no beneficial result was obtained. It will thus be evident from the foregoing observations that up till now the conditions for obtaining uniformly good results from molasses as a manure and the mechanism of the process have not been worked out. In this as well as in previous publications (Dhar and Mukerji, *Proc. Acad. Sci. U.P.*, 1934, 4, 175; 1935, 4, 330; 1935, 5, 61) we have established that the oxidation of the carbohydrates present in molasses either through the agency of bacteria or sunlight or induction and the intermediate products to carbon-dioxide and water liberates energy in the soil and this energy is utilised in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen and that is why the ammonia and the total nitrogen contents increase and thus beneficial results in the growth of crops are obtained with molasses as fertiliser. Moreover, as molasses, contain lime, potash and phosphates, its fertilising value is also increased by the presence of these substances. It is interesting to note here that previous workers determined only the total nitrogen of the soil after the addition of energy-rich

compounds, and as the difference in total nitrogen is not very high before and after the addition of energy-rich compounds to the soil, they were doubtful regarding the fixation of nitrogen in the soil by the addition of energy-rich compounds. But as we have estimated, both the available (ammoniacal and nitric nitrogen) and the total nitrogen, we have been able to detect the increase of available nitrogen and also total nitrogen in all cases when energy-rich organic compounds are added to well-aerated soils.

It has already been stated that many workers have failed to obtain beneficial results with molasses. Our experiments show that the failure is due to insufficiency of oxidation of the carbohydrates caused by the lack of the aeration of the soil. When the aeration of the soil is insufficient, the increase of ammonia is less and the soil becomes acidic. The amount of fixation of nitrogen depends on the energy available from the oxidation of the carbohydrates of molasses and the bye-products formed from the partial oxidation of carbohydrates and that is why sufficient oxygen is necessary for obtaining beneficial results, and this is achieved if the soil is dug or turned over once a week or 10 days during the period of eight to twelve weeks between the application of molasses to the field and the sowing of crops.

In cold countries, the soil temperature being low and due to lack of sunshine, the velocity of the oxidation of energy-rich substances present in the molasses is small and thus the energy available from the oxidation of carbohydrates may be too small for any marked nitrogen fixation. That is why, many workers like Pfeiffer and Blanck, Hutchinson and others were unable to find beneficial effects with sugars. Moreover, in temperate climates, *Azotobacter* is not suitable for nitrogen fixation, as the fixation at 10° and lower temperatures is practically nothing. The soil temperature in colder countries being lower than 10° most of the time in the year, practically no nitrogen fixation by *Azotobacter* is possible and that is why *Azotobacter* has not been utilised by agriculturists in cold countries. Thiele (*Landw. Versuchs-Stat.*, 1905, 63, 161) measured the soil temperatures of arable and grass lands daily for three years at Breslau, Germany and reported that only rarely were they favourable for *Azotobacter*. In tropical countries, however, if the soil is well ploughed after the addition of molasses, there is no reason why soil fertility regarding combined nitrogen should not be increased. We have applied molasses to more than 30 plots of land in different

portions of the University compound and in several fields in Cawnpore and we have always observed marked increase in the ammonia and total nitrogen contents of the soils on the application of molasses. In most of our field experiments the amount of ammonia after the addition of molasses and aeration has become three times the amount originally present in the soil. Also *Azotobacter* requires more heat than *Bacillus radicolica* and several other bacteria and is eminently suitable for nitrogen fixation in tropical countries except in the months of May and June when the soil temperature in the day time exceeds 50°, beyond which *Azotobacter* is unable to fix nitrogen. This bacteria should be widely utilised in the fixation of nitrogen in tropical countries when fed with energy-rich substances like molasses, press cakes, etc.

Molasses in the Conservation of Soil Nitrogen.

Apart from the fixation of nitrogen, molasses act as a protector of soil nitrogen and appears to be more effective as a soil fertilizer than ammonium sulphate alone, specially in tropical countries. Our experiments recorded in Tables XI, XII and XIII, show that the loss of nitrogen from the soil on adding ammonium sulphate is decreased when along with ammonium sulphate molasses is added. We have shown that when ammonium sulphate is added to soil in shallow enamelled dishes and exposed to sunlight in the months of May, June and July at Allahabad, as much as 60% of the ammonium salt is lost. This loss can be minimised by adding molasses along with ammonium sulphate. It appears, therefore, that the value of ammonium sulphate or urea as a manure to be used in tropical countries is likely to be greatly enhanced if it is mixed with molasses or any other carbonaceous material. From the foregoing lines, it will be clear why farmyard manure or green manure produces better results in crop yields than ammonium sulphate, because the carbonaceous substances present in the farmyard or green manure, markedly retards the velocity of the oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds present in the farmyard and green manures and retard the processes of ammonification and nitrification and act as an agent in conservation of the nitrogen added. Oil cakes containing fats and nitrogenous substances ought to be effective as a nitrogenous manure in tropical countries, because fats are known to retard the oxidation of nitrogenous compounds.

Russell ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth," 1932, pp. 76-78 and 313-361) has reported that the yield of barley and straw with farmyard manure in the Rothamsted field experiments from 1852-1922 is better than that obtained with complete artificial manures containing ammonium salts, potassium salts and phosphates. This is due to the fact that there is more nitrogen in the field manured with cowdung than with artificials as is evident from the following data from the Rothamsted fields:—

TABLE IX.

	Total N.
(1) Receiving no manure since 1843	0.095%
(2) Receiving farmyard manure since 1852	0.256
(3) Receiving complete artificials $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.099
(4) Receiving complete farmyard manure	0.253
(5) Receiving potash & phosphate but no nitrogen	0.090

TABLE X.

Total nitrogen balance-sheet (1865-1914) in the top nine inches of soil.

	Farmyard manure.	Without manure.	Complete Plot 7	artificials. Plot 13
Total N in soil in 1865 lb/acre.	4850	2960	3390	3320
" " " per cent.	0.196	0.114	0.123	0.121
" " in 1914 lb/acre.	5590	2570	3210	3240
" " " per cent.	0.236	0.092	0.120	0.122
Total change in 4 years lb/acre.	+740	-390	-180	-80

In order to investigate the retarding influence of molasses on the loss of nitrogen from soils, the following field experiments were performed. 270 G., 540 g. and 1080 g. of ammonium sulphate dissolved in water were applied to three plots on 26th September, 1935, the area of each plot being 144 sq. ft. To three other plots, the same amounts of ammonium sulphate were added along with 12 kilograms of molasses (i.e., at the rate of 3600 kilograms per acre). All these plots were ploughed before the application of the ammonium sulphate and were dug once in 10 days afterwards. From time to time, the ammoniacal nitric and total nitrogen and total carbon were estimated. The following results were obtained.

TABLE XI.

 270 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 144 sq. ft. of land used.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N.}$	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Unmolassed	0.00832%	0.00350%	0.01182%	0.0583%	0.416%	27-9-35
Molassed	0.00814	0.00350	0.01164	0.0588	0.587	"
Unmolassed	0.00636	0.00556	0.01192	0.0583	0.416	12-10-35
Molassed	0.00778	0.00426	0.01204	0.0609	0.578	"
Unmolassed	0.00608	0.00600	0.01208	0.0538	0.416	24-10-35
Molassed	0.00778	0.00582	0.01360	0.0625	0.501	"
Unmolassed	0.00438	0.00714	0.01152	0.0538	0.411	7-11-35
Molassed	0.00700	0.00636	0.01336	0.0636	0.498	"
Unmolassed	0.00420	0.00714	0.01130	0.0538	0.412	13-12-35
Molassed	0.0064	0.0064	0.0128	0.0634	0.500	"

TABLE XII.

 540 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 144 sq. ft. of land used.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N.}$	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C.	Date of analysis.
Unmolassed	0.01206%	0.00344%	0.01550%	0.0603%	0.417%	27-9-35
Molassed	0.01228	0.00344	0.01572	0.0608	0.587	"
Unmolassed	0.00768	0.00636	0.01404	0.0609	0.416	12-10-35
Molassed	0.01076	0.00436	0.01512	0.0636	0.573	"
Unmolassed	0.00754	0.00636	0.01390	0.0593	0.421	24-10-35
Molassed	0.01000	0.00636	0.01636	0.0673	0.507	"
Unmolassed	0.00538	0.00776	0.01314	0.0583	0.418	7-11-35
Molassed	0.00896	0.00874	0.01770	0.0667	0.502	"
Unmolassed	0.00502	0.0078	0.01282	0.0583	0.418	13-12-35
Molassed	0.00880	0.0088	0.0176	0.0667	0.500	"
Unmolassed	0.00488	0.0080	0.01288	0.0574	0.422	10-1-36
Molassed	0.0080	0.0080	0.016	0.067	0.512	"

TABLE XIII.

1080 G. of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ per 144 sq. ft. of land used.

Condition.	$\text{NH}_3\text{-N.}$	Nitric-N.	Available N.	Total N.	Total C	Date of analysis.
Unmolassed	0.02032%	0.00356%	0.02388%	0.0757%	0.416%	27-9-35
Molassed	0.02044	0.00384	0.02428	0.0757	0.585	"
Unmolassed	0.00874	0.00932	0.01806	0.0700	0.416	12-10-35
Molassed	0.0140	0.00636	0.02036	0.0760	0.574	"
Unmolassed	0.00754	0.01040	0.01794	0.0636	0.416	24-10-35
Molassed	0.01272	0.00874	0.02146	0.0823	0.574	"
Unmolassed	0.00636	0.01166	0.01802	0.0612	0.422	7-11-35
Molassed	0.01000	0.00972	0.01972	0.0828	0.552	"
Unmolassed	0.00578	0.0116	0.01738	0.0610	0.422	13-12-35
Molassed	0.0096	0.0098	0.0194	0.0830	0.542	"
Unmolassed	0.0056	0.01144	0.01704	0.0596	0.422	10-1-36
Molassed	0.008	0.0100	0.0180	0.0842	0.532	"

The foregoing results show very well that the total and the available nitrogen of the molassed plots are always greater than those in the unmolassed plots. Hence molasses acts as a nitrogen sparer in the soil and this is a very important application of molasses.

The above results also show that molasses can fix nitrogen in the soil even in presence of ammonium salts, as the total nitrogen in the soil containing molasses and ammonium sulphate is greater in the end than in the beginning.

The following experiments showing the retarding influence of cane sugar on nitrification and nitrogen loss from soils containing ammonium sulphate were carried on in open enamelled dishes:—

TABLE XIV.

Original soil contained 0.00356% $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, 0.0021% nitric-N, 0.0466% total-N and 0.5134% C.

	Time of exposure.		
	62 hours.	132 hours.	200 hours.
1. 200 G. soil + 16 g. cane sugar	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.005\% \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.05 \\ \text{Total-C} = 4.221 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0070\% \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.0498 \\ 3.187 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0084\% \\ 0.0029 \\ 0.0499 \\ 1.882 \end{array} \right.$
2. 200 G. soil + 16 g. cane sugar + 8g. Na_3PO_4	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.00582 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.484 \\ \text{Total-C} = 4.00 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.00728 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.0498 \\ 3.178 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0089 \\ 0.0029 \\ 0.0499 \\ 1.761 \end{array} \right.$
3. 200 G. soil + 16g. cane sugar + 0.04 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.0875 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.1842 \\ \text{Total-C} = 4.114. \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0668 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.175 \\ 2.991 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0624 \\ 0.0030 \\ 0.148 \\ 1.892 \end{array} \right.$
4. 200 G. soil + 16g. cane sugar + 0.4g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ + 8 g. NO_3PO_4	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.08824 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.2002 \\ \text{Total-C} = 4.128 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0642 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.178 \\ 2.991 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0604 \\ 0.0030 \\ 0.152 \\ 1.88 \end{array} \right.$
5. 200 G. soil + 16g. cane sugar + 2 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.028 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.116 \\ \text{Total-C} = 4.112 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.017 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.1112 \\ 3.019 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0156 \\ 0.0029 \\ 0.1167 \\ 1.885 \end{array} \right.$
6. 200 G. soil + 16g. cane sugar + 0.2 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ + 8 g. Na_3PO_4	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.0291 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.1169 \\ \text{Total-C} = 4.121 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.014 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.1181 \\ 3.029 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.015 \\ 0.0029 \\ 0.1172 \\ 1.721 \end{array} \right.$
7. 200 G. soil + 16g. cane sugar + 0.1 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.01 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.0934 \\ \text{Total-C} = 3.914 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.00934 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.0934 \\ 2.871 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.00932 \\ 0.0029 \\ 0.0934 \\ 1.895 \end{array} \right.$
8. 200 G. soil + 16g. cane sugar + 0.1 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ + 8 g. Na_3PO_4	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.01 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.0028 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.9333 \\ \text{Total-C} = 3.992 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.00922 \\ 0.0028 \\ 0.057 \\ 2.881 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0091 \\ 0.0029 \\ 0.0944 \\ 1.778 \end{array} \right.$
9. 200 G. soil + 0.4 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.04516 \\ \text{NO}_3\text{-N} = 0.00362 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.1346 \\ \text{Total-C} = 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0233 \\ 0.00388 \\ 0.123 \\ 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.02024 \\ 0.00422 \\ 0.0928 \\ 0.506 \end{array} \right.$
10. 200 G. soil + 0.2 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.0232 \\ \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.00278 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.1072 \\ \text{Total-C} = 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.014 \\ 0.005 \\ 0.1060 \\ 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.01336 \\ 0.00516 \\ 0.0875 \\ 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$
11. 200 G. soil + 0.1 g. N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.00822 \\ \text{NH}_3\text{-N} = 0.00406 \\ \text{Total-N} = 0.0778 \\ \text{Total-C} = 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0082 \\ 0.005 \\ 0.0772 \\ 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0.0082 \\ 0.005 \\ 0.07 \\ 0.5068 \end{array} \right.$

The foregoing results show that the total nitrogen in vessels containing cane sugar and ammonium sulphate is always greater than in the corresponding ones containing ammonium sulphate alone. Thus cane sugar acts as a sparer of the soil nitrogen. It has been generally believed that organic substances like sugars when added to soil causes anaerobic denitrification but in none of our experiments, we observed any denitrification of this type with molasses or cane sugar added to the soil, which is exposed to light and air.

According to Lyon and Wilson (Cornell University Agricultural Experiment Station Memoirs, 1928, 115) nitrogen balance is not maintained but loss of nitrogen takes place when the crops grown during autumn only are ploughed in followed by a summer fallow. On the other hand, gain of nitrogen is observed in the soil under grass and not disturbed for summer fallow. The observations of Howard and Wad ("Waste Products of Agriculture," 1931, p. 100) show that a certain amount of nitrogen fixation also takes place in the composting of the waste products of agriculture according to the Indore method of composting, when the aeration in the compost heaps is sufficient. It appears that in the oxidation of the carbonaceous substances in the compost heaps, energy is liberated as is evident from the heat produced in these heaps and a part of this energy of oxidation is utilised in the fixation of nitrogen. It has been reported that when molasses is added to growing plants, harmful results are produced. This can be easily explained from the following considerations:—

The small amounts of nitrate, which is the real plant food present in the soil, reacts with the carbohydrates present in the molasses with the formation of ammonium salts through the agency of bacteria as is well known, or light as established by Dhar and Mukherji. Moreover, the ammonium salts may be eaten up by the increased growth of the micro-organisms caused by the addition of energy-rich carbohydrates of the molasses. In this way the available nitrogen of the soil may be lost to the crops. Moreover, the oxidation of the carbohydrates generates heat in the soil and both these results may be prejudicial to the growth of plants. The workers at Java have shown empirically that the carbohydrates present in the molasses were the real factors in improving soil fertility, because the effect produced by an equivalent amount of potash, phosphates, lime and combined nitrogen is insignificant. The experience of workers in other sugar producing countries shows that an interval of some weeks between the addition of molasses to the soil and the growth of crops on this soil seems necessary.

From our results it is clear that sufficient time is necessary for the oxidation of carbohydrates added with molasses leading to the maximum amount of ammonia formation and increase of total nitrogen in the soil. The carbohydrates must be oxidised in order that the nitrogen may be fixed and as this process takes time, an interval of 8 to 12 weeks, depending on the amounts of molasses added, is absolutely necessary.

The workers at Java have reported the formation of organic acids in the incipient stage after the addition of molasses to the soil. This observation has been confirmed by Vhaskaran and Narasimhamurti, Subrahmanyam and Sundara Ayengar (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 1, 155) who have reported the production of acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid etc. under water logged conditions. We have observed that traces of alcohol and small amounts of organic acids are produced when molasses or cane sugar are added to the soil in presence of air, but a good deal of the sugars added with molasses is oxidised completely to carbon dioxide and water. Most of the intermediate products are also energy-rich and are oxidised to carbon dioxide in course of time on the soil surface. Hence large amounts of energy are available for the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the soil on the addition of molasses and proper æration.

Molasses in the Reclamation of Alkali Soils.

A systematic investigation is in progress in these laboratories for the reclamation of alkali soils by the application of molasses. It is well known that molasses contain between 60 to 65% carbohydrates, 4.5% potash, 2% lime, 0.5% phosphoric acid, 0.5% silica, 0.5% iron and aluminium oxides and 0.5% combined nitrogen and the rest, water. Moreover, molasses is distinctly acidic. Research work carried on in Allahabad, Bangalore, Java, and Hawaii shows that when molasses is added to the soil, along with carbonic acid, organic acids, like acetic, propionic, butyric, lactic etc., are produced in the early stages of the decomposition and partial oxidation of the carbohydrates present in molasses. Consequently the acids present in molasses and those obtained from the decomposition and partial oxidation can neutralise the alkali of the soils rich in alkali. Moreover, the carbonic acid, which is produced in large amounts from the decomposition and oxidation of carbohydrates, can convert the sodium carbonate of the alkali soils into bicarbonate. Also, in the

process of the escape of carbon dioxide from the molassed soil, the latter is rendered porous and its tilth is improved. Our researches show definitely that the moisture content of the molassed soil, is appreciably higher than that of the unmolassed one. The lime which is added to the soil along with molasses is rendered soluble by the organic acids formed from the molasses and is helpful in the conversion of the sodium soil into the calcium one. Molasses when added to soil also increases the total nitrogen, ammonia contents, the micro-organisms, the humus water retention capacity and the calcium salts, which are readily soluble. All these factors go towards the reclamation of the alkali soils on the addition of molasses. The soluble calcium salts are helpful in the improvement of the soil tilth by their precipitation power on the clay particles. Moreover, in presence of soluble calcium salts, the permeability of the soils is greatly improved.

Molasses to the extent of 100-300 maunds per acre has been applied to some alkaline fields near Cawnpore, Allahabad and Mysore and beneficial results in their reclamation have been obtained. Our results show that molasses is a better reclaiming agent for alkaline lands than either gypsum or powdered sulphur. There is nitrogen loss for soils when these latter reclaiming agents are added to the alkaline lands, whilst molasses adds nitrogen. The reclaiming effect of molasses is much quicker than that of gypsum or powdered sulphur.

*Influence of Ammonium salts and Nitrates on the Nitrogen
Fixation in Soils by the Addition of Molasses.*

A very important fact has been brought out by our researches namely, that the amount of ammonium salts obtained by fixation depends on the quantities of the available and possibly total nitrogen originally present in the soil before the addition of molasses or cane sugar. Thus in our first set of experiments with pure cane sugar when added to unsterile soil and exposed to sunlight, the ammoniacal nitrogen rose to 0.0186% from 0.00126% originally present in the soil, which contained 0.00164% available nitrogen. In the second series of experiments the ammoniacal nitrogen increased from 0.00192% to 0.0162% and the total available nitrogen in the soil was 0.00392%.

Similarly with molasses, the fixation was less as it contained some ammonium salts.

Our results show that in presence of ammonium sulphate or

potassium nitrate, the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the soil on the addition of cane sugar and molasses may be small.

It appears, therefore, that in soils, containing a larger percentage of available nitrogen, the fixation due to the addition of energy rich compounds is less marked. In tropical countries, however, the nitrogen fixation on the addition of molasses or other carbonaceous compounds is likely to be always prominent, as the ammonia and total nitrogen contents of tropical soils are low.

Efficiency of the Nitrogen Fixation Processes of Different kinds.

It is well known that approximately 1% of the energy available in the oxidation of carbohydrates is utilised in the fixation of nitrogen in presence of *Azotobacter*. In Table III it will be seen that the efficiency of nitrogen fixation in the induced oxidation of glucose or cane sugar in presence of ferrous hydroxide is of the same order as in the bacterial fixation. Further work on the efficiency of bacterial, photochemical and catalytic nitrogen fixation is in progress.

It appears that a large amount of molasses produced in the country has to be applied in agriculture for improving sugarcane, rice, wheat and other products. Our experiments show that molasses can serve as an excellent fertiliser in the cultivation of rice and other crops, thus by the application of 3600 kilograms of molasses per acre of land and digging and watering the soil once every week for two months (May and June 1935), 14.1 maunds of *Aus* paddy and 26.9 maunds of straw were obtained in the molassed land, while 8.5 maunds paddy and 22.4 maunds straw were grown in the control land.

SUMMARY.

1. When cane sugar solutions and sterilised soil are exposed to sunlight for a long time in quartz vessels under sterile conditions, there is appreciable increase in the available and total nitrogen contents of the sterile soil.

2. Experiments show that 4 mg. of nitrogen are fixed as ammonia per gram of glucose or cane sugar oxidised by passing air through solutions of these carbohydrates in presence of ferrous hydroxide. It appears that the efficiency of nitrogen fixation obtained in the induced oxidation of carbohydrates is of the same order as that with cultures of *Azotobacter* thriving in flasks containing solutions of energy-rich compounds.

3. When cane sugar solution is added to ordinary soils and exposed to sunlight and air, the ammoniacal and total nitrogen are increased.

4. When molasses in different amounts are added to soils in dishes and exposed to sunlight and air, the ammoniacal and total nitrogen are also increased. This increase of nitrogen is always greater in sunlight than in the dark.

5. Our experimental results show that in the photochemical or induced oxidation of carbohydrates, nitrogen fixation can take place. The oxidation of energy-rich organic compounds by air, either by light absorption or by chemical induction or by bacterial action, causes the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen. It appears, therefore, that in tropical countries in ordinary soils, the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by the addition of energy-rich compounds is partially bacterial and partially photochemical and catalytic.

6. Field experiments with molasses when mixed with soil, show that there is an appreciable increase in the total nitrogen and ammoniacal nitrogen contents. The amount of ammoniacal nitrogen goes on increasing up to a limiting value when it decreases. But at this stage, the nitric nitrogen increases due to the oxidation of the ammonium salts formed from nitrogen fixation, and the C : N ratio tends to approach the normal value. This is the time when crops are to be sown on the molassed fields. Using 10800 kg. of molasses per acre of land and digging or turning over once in 10 days, the land is ready for crops in about 12 weeks ; with 3600 to 7200 kilogram per acre it is suitable in about 8 weeks. In all our field trials with molasses as a fertilizer, we have always observed an increase of total and available nitrogen. Moreover, as molasses contain potash, phosphate, lime and as nitrogen is fixed in molassed lands, it is an excellent fertilizer for tropical soils.

7. The moisture contents of molassed lands are always greater than in the unmolassed ones.

8. Excellent composts containing double the amount of total nitrogen as is originally present in the soil have been obtained by mixing molasses with soil in heaps, which are exposed to air and light.

9. The available and total nitrogen of soils, which have been molassed for two consecutive years, are greater than in soils molassed once. It seems, therefore, that molasses exerts residual effect on the soil.

10. This new method of nitrogen fixation based on the principle of the utilisation of the energy available from the oxidation of carbohydrates and other organic compounds in the soil should be largely

utilised in tropical countries, where the velocity of the oxidation of substances in the soil is high under ordinary conditions due to the high temperatures and light absorption.

11. In cold countries, the soil temperature being low and due to the lack of sunshine, the velocity of the oxidation of energy-rich substances present in the molasses may be small and thus the energy available from the oxidation of carbohydrates may be too small for any marked nitrogen fixation. Moreover in temperate climates, *Azotobacter* is not suitable for nitrogen fixation, as our experiments and those carried on in other countries show that nitrogen fixation by *Azotobacter* at 10° and lower temperatures is practically nothing and *Azotobacter* requires more heat than most other bacteria and that is why *Azotobacter* has not been utilised by agriculturists in cold countries for nitrogen fixation.

12. *Azotobacter* should be widely utilised in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the soil of tropical countries when fed with energy-rich substances like molasses, press cakes etc.

13. Our results obtained with ammonium sulphate added to the soil with and without molasses show that the total and available nitrogen of the molassed plots are always greater than those in the unmolassed plots. Hence molasses not only fix nitrogen in the soil but also act as a sparer of nitrogen in the soil and this is a very important application of molasses.

14. Cane sugar has also been found to act as a sparer of soil nitrogen. When molasses or cane sugar is added to the soil exposed to light and air, there is no evidence of anærobic denitrification in all our experiments, although it has been generally believed that in such cases, anærobic denitrification sets in.

15. Molasses has been found to be a better reclaiming agent for alkaline fields than gypsum or powdered sulphur.

16. It seems probable that nitrogen fixation takes place in animal or plant respiration.

17. It appears that in ærobic nitrogen fixation through the agencies of bacteria, light and chemical induction, the nitrogen and oxygen combine forming nitrate, which in its turn is converted into ammonia and small amounts of amino acids.

18. Greater yields of rice and sugarcane have been obtained with molasses as a manure.